

Teaching Foreign Languages in Non-Philological Universities

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the issues based on teaching foreign languages in non-philological universities. A professionally oriented approach is understood as the maximum representation of the professional sphere in teaching a foreign language, immersing students in a foreign language professional context at the levels of: content (foreign language material of a professional orientation), activity (implementation, implementation of fragments of professional activity in foreign language classes). The developed private methodological principles of teaching reflect the compliance of the system of training in a foreign language in a non-linguistic university with the social order in the field of this profession.

Key words: foreign language, professional oriented education, non-philological universities, professional context.

INTRODUCTION

The history of the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages in non-philological universities reflect the history of changing approaches to learning in search of the most effective scientific and methodological concept. However, the change in approaches to teaching foreign languages in higher education must be considered in the broad context of what is happening in society in general and in the field of education in particular, since the need for reforms is due to the need to adapt the education system to the socio-economic needs of society.

Social, economic and political transformations in our country, the integration of education into the world educational space, the signing of the Bologna Declaration by Uzbekistan have actualized the task of further modernization of the system of higher professional education in general and foreign language education in particular.

DISCUSSIONS

The effectiveness of the professional and language education of a future specialist is largely determined by the educational concept adopted in society at a certain stage of its development and the model of specialist training built on its basis. Since the dominant approach in education, in fact, determines the logic of the implementation of a particular model of education in a certain subject area, including such as a foreign language, therefore, the issue of modernizing foreign language education in non-linguistic universities from the standpoint of a competency-based approach becomes relevant.

Thus, in a new socially, politically and economically changed country, it became necessary to develop a different system of language education in a higher professional school, different from the existing one, since the level of foreign language proficiency by graduates of non-linguistic universities does not meet the requirements of the modern educational concept, modern society, and the market work, as evidenced by numerous publications on this problem (Zh.L. Vitlin, I.L. Bim, E.I. Passov, T.N. Astafurova, T.B. Lesokhina, R.P. Milrud, Yu.V. Eremin, E.N. Solovova, etc.) and practical experience of teaching a foreign language in these universities.

In addition, the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages in non-linguistic universities has been going through a difficult period since the early 1990s. On the one hand, the prestige of the discipline "foreign language" is

constantly increasing, and on the other hand, a number of serious problems that departments of foreign languages constantly face prevent professionally-oriented teaching of foreign languages in universities. These include:

- Insufficient number of hours allocated for practical training and their irrational distribution;

- different level of foreign language training of applicants: a) insufficient preparation of the majority of first-year students or its complete absence (10%); b) the presence of a group of students with special training - graduates of specialized schools and classes with in-depth study of a foreign language; the lack of special teaching aids for the last group of students and the insufficient number of modern manuals for all groups;

- the lack of development of the problems of teaching a foreign language to students of non-linguistic universities in close connection with the profession they receive due to the lack of interdisciplinary coordination between the departments of the foreign language and the main departments of universities;

- the inability of students to use the already acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in a foreign language, as well as methods of activity to solve practical problems.

The problem is of serious concern, since in modern conditions the formation of knowledge is not the main goal of learning (knowledge for the sake of knowledge). Knowledge, skills and abilities as units of educational result are necessary but not sufficient to be a successful specialist in the modern information society. For a specialist, it is not so much encyclopedic literacy that is important, but the ability to apply generalized knowledge, skills and abilities in a foreign language to resolve specific situations and problems that arise in the real activity of professional communication.

The expansion of trade and economic relations with foreign countries, a large amount of specialized literature in foreign languages, the possibility of obtaining professionally significant information on the Internet, the international exchange of students and specialists, obtaining or continuing education in foreign universities, etc. requires a competent modern specialist knowledge of a foreign language for the purposes of professional communication in a foreign language.

Therefore, based on the analysis of the literature and the practice of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university, it can be argued that in the last decade, significant contradictions have become more and more clearly identified between: the social order of society for a competent specialist who knows at least one foreign language for its practical use in professional activities, and existing approaches to teaching a foreign language in non-linguistic universities; the increased need of the individual to improve the level of knowledge of a foreign language, on the one hand, and the practice of teaching a foreign language in non-linguistic universities, on the other hand, has not justified itself.

Thus, the problem is to resolve the contradiction between the importance of foreign language professional training of a specialist and the insufficient level of its provision in a non-linguistic university.

We see the solution to this problem in changing the approach to teaching foreign languages in non-linguistic universities. We believe that the way to achieve a new quality of foreign language education is a competency-based approach that meets the requirements of the modernization of professional education, the social order of society and the latest achievements in the field of methods of teaching foreign languages.

Foreign language communicative competence is the willingness of students to use the acquired knowledge, skills, abilities in a foreign language to solve practical

and theoretical problems in life. At the same time, any skills are acquired in the process of activity, therefore, the formation of competence is possible only in the course of a variety of cognitive, communicative, practical, creative activities of students. That is why the competence-based approach is aimed at gaining experience of such activities for students, at giving the very process of learning an activity character. The main thing is to be able to acquire knowledge not passively, but actively (actively), that is, by making efforts, and be able to use this knowledge in everyday life, both within and outside university education.

In the methodology of teaching a foreign language, various approaches have been developed and are widely used, expressing the specifics of this area of didactics.

One of these approaches is the linguistic and regional approach, the founders of which were E.M. Vereshchagin and V.G. Kostomarov [4]. For the first time in the national methodology, these scientists expressed and substantiated the idea of the need for an integrated study of the language and the national culture of its speakers. In the context of the approach under consideration, the vocabulary of the studied foreign language seems to be the leading source of linguistic and cultural information. In this regard, the main attention of scientists is paid to the study of equivalent and non-equivalent lexical concepts, terminological and background vocabulary, phraseological units.

In modern linguodidactics, much attention is paid to the intercultural approach, the essence of which is revealed in the studies of such scientists as E.M. Vereshchagin, V.G. Kostomarov, V.V. Safonova (2004), I.I. Khaleeva and others. In their opinion, this approach ensures the formation of the skills and abilities of students to interact with representatives of other countries in a dialogue of different cultures.

One of the new approaches currently being developed is a multilingual approach aimed at developing the skills of multilingual communication, recognizing and understanding the peculiarities of foreign cultural realities of multilingual participants in multicultural communication.

However, scientists are currently focusing on the development of more effective methodological approaches to foreign language teaching of students, reflecting qualitative changes in the system of higher education, which in turn are associated with the introduction of activity methodology.

The activity approach (L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev, M.I. Makhmutov, D.B. Elkonin, etc.), as well as the personal-activity approach (E.V. Bondarevskaya, I.A. Zimnyaya, A. V. Khutorskoy and others) methodologically express the idea that the categories of "activity" and "personality" are inextricably linked: a person arises and is formed only in the process of human activity. In accordance with this approach, in linguodidactics, productive speech activity is considered as a necessary condition for the development of the student's personality, therefore, the main goal of teaching a foreign language is the formation of foreign language speech activity, which involves the gradual mastering of the skills and abilities of various speech actions by students, the development of motivation for speech foreign language communication.

The effectiveness of professional and language education of future specialists, graduates of a higher professional school, is largely determined by the educational concept adopted in society at a certain stage of its development, which today is considered a competence-based approach.

This study theoretically substantiates the need and possibility of introducing a competence-based approach to the process of teaching a foreign language in non-linguistic universities, reveals its essence and main fundamental provisions.

Of great importance for this study was the analysis of existing classifications of approaches to teaching a foreign language, as a result of which the following were substantiated: a) the need to introduce a competency-based approach to the process of teaching a foreign language in a higher professional school; and b) the complex integrative essence of the competency-based approach to teaching a foreign language in non-philological universities, which is systemic, interdisciplinary, combines personal, activity, competency-based aspects in an effective, relevant to the current state of science, training system that has a practical and pragmatic orientation.

The paper considered the main aspects of the competency-based approach and determined: the component composition of the professional competence of a specialist (a graduate of a non-linguistic university) and its integral component - a foreign language professional and communicative competence of a specialist.

The foreign language professional and communicative competence of a specialist is presented in the study as a set of competencies that provides the possibility of effective interaction of a future specialist with the outside world in a specific area of professional activity.

The essence of the competence-based approach to teaching a foreign language to students of non-linguistic universities is considered in this study as a set of general provisions and principles that determine the main changes in the components of the foreign language teaching system: goals, selection of content, organization of the learning process, choice of technologies and evaluation of learning outcomes - formulated in logic his conceptual ideas.

The implementation of a competency-based approach to teaching a foreign language in non-linguistic universities is possible if, from the standpoint of the competency-based, activity-based and personal components of the competency-

based approach, the goal and result of teaching a foreign language are reoriented towards the formation of a foreign language professional and communicative competence of future specialists in trade and economic profile.

Modernization of the content of teaching a foreign language in non-linguistic universities from the standpoint of a competency-based approach is possible if its selection is based on the principles of: effective-target orientation; professional orientation, interdisciplinary integration and coordination; communication; authenticity, and the change in its organization will take place on the basis of the principle of modularity.

The implementation of the competence-based approach in the practice of teaching a foreign language to students of non-linguistic universities will increase the efficiency of the learning process, provided that it is built taking into account the following principles: the activity nature of the learning process; student-centered orientation of learning and continuity of learning.

Mastering the modernized content of teaching a foreign language in non-linguistic universities is possible subject to the use of the developed technology, which is a sequence of teaching and learning activities that ensure the formation of a foreign language professional and communicative competence of a specialist through the communication of professional knowledge by means of a foreign language and the formation of his professional qualities, including effective methods of mastering the selected content and exercise system.

In our opinion, the implementation of all the identified principles of the competency-based approach causes qualitative changes in all elements of the methodological system of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university, which makes it possible to increase the effectiveness of the learning process.

Thus, professionally-oriented training of specialists in a foreign language from the standpoint of a competency-based approach should not only provide a certain level of knowledge, skills and abilities of students in a foreign language, but also form their readiness to perform foreign language activities in the process of solving practical and theoretical problems, as well as for further self-development and self-education, i.e. foreign language professional and communicative competence. The application of the proposed technology of teaching a foreign language allows students of non-linguistic universities of economic orientation to form a foreign language professional and communicative competence, which is necessary and communicative-sufficient for solving educational and professional problems of foreign language communication.

References:

1. Belkin A.S. Competence. Professionalism. Mastery. Chelyabinsk. 2004
2. Verbitsky A.A. Competency-Based Approach and Theory of Contextual Learning: Materials for the fourth meeting of the methodological seminar November 16, 2004. M.: Research Center for the Problems of Quality in Training Specialists, 2004
3. Vilensky M.Ya., Obraztsov P.I., Uman A.I. Technologies of professionally oriented education in higher education: Textbook. 2004
4. Vygotsky JI.C. Selected psychological studies. M., 1956
5. Galperin P.Ya. Teaching methods and mental development of the child. M., 1985.
6. Galskova N.D. Modern methods of teaching foreign languages. A guide for the teacher. - M .: ARKTI, 2000

7. Gez N.I. Formation of communicative competence as an object of foreign methodological research // Inostr. languages at school., 1985
8. Zeer E.F. Psychological and didactic constructs of the quality of professional education / Education and science. 2002, No. 2(14)